

Heal Talk

Endo

Talk

Minimal Invasive Endodontics

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A successful root canal procedure increases the likelihood that the tooth will continue to function normally within the mouth for a significant amount of time. After endodontic treatment, the lifetime of a tooth is dependent on the amount of residual tissue and healing. However, there are many other factors that impact endodontic outcomes such as the quality of the restoration and structural integrity of the tooth after root canal preparation. The remaining dental structure and restorations have a significant impact on the long-term viability of an endodontically treated tooth. Minimally invasive endodontics (MIE) is an endodontic technique that aims to maintain as much of the healthy coronal, cervical, and radicular tooth structure as possible. This innovative kind of root canal therapy, known as minimally invasive endodontics (MIE), takes a different approach that focuses on minimizing structural alterations after treatment. Treatment and prevention of pulpal diseases and apical periodontitis, as well as preserving as much good tissue as possible, are all part of the MIE method, which is safe, accurate, and time-saving. Endodontic procedures are becoming less invasive because of the development of new materials and technology, such as cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) scans, advanced microscopes, unique access designs, and inventive access cavities. Access opening, root canal cleaning and shaping, and surgical endodontics are all possible applications for MIE in endodontic treatment. The objective of new-age endodontics is minimum intervention. A favourable outcome with minimally invasive treatment may be achieved while preserving the tooth's natural structure with careful case selection. The concept of minimally invasive endodontics calls for the treatment and prevention of pulpal pathoses and apical periodontitis, while causing the least amount of change to the dental hard tissues. This preserves the strength and function of the endodontically treated tooth with the intent that it will last the patient's lifetime.

Just as in medicine, the dental surgeon treating endodontic disease must develop new skills and dexterity in order to adapt to a limited working environment within the confines of the pulpal space. These skills include working with new instruments and irrigants for cleaning the system; utilising

advanced imaging modalities and computer software for demonstrating both the complexities of the root canal system and improving the accuracy of techniques; employing increased magnification and lighting for visualising the pulpal space as well as applying new materials that enhance the prognosis for restoring structure and retaining the natural dentition.

Preserving structural integrity

Some of the ideas in the way dentistry has been practiced over the past century have recently undergone a paradigm shift. The tooth's residual structural integrity is a critical component in determining prognosis in terms of future function after restoration. The purpose of all restorative therapies, notably in endodontics, is to maintain strength and stiffness that resists structural deformation. For example, extension for prevention is no longer found to be widely accepted, as it requires removal of the sound and intact tooth structure for only a potential chance of a future benefit. Understanding the biomechanical behaviour of dentin as the weakest link in any restorative system is essential if we are to avoid causing more harm to it.

There have been cases when endodontically treated teeth were extracted because of inadequate repair of the dental structure. It has been found that a tooth with extensive enamel and dentin loss performs much worse than an undamaged tooth when it comes to the capacity to bear occlusal and functional forces. Reduced access preparation diameter by half resulted in the operator removing four times less tooth structure in MIE compared to a standard preparation. A higher density of dentin boosted the tooth's tensile and fracture strength, making it more resistant to breakage. Based on logical reasoning, the preservation of maximal dentine mass during access cavity preparation and root canal shaping is of utmost importance; to date, no manufactured substance can effectively compensate for the lost dentinal tissue because of its unique features and traits. Endodontic therapy can also affect the lifespan of endodontic treatment, tooth rehabilitation, and biomechanics during oral function. Several factors and clinical judgments must be followed while recovering endodontically treated teeth. The choice of fiberglass posts and restorative materials is influenced by several criteria,

including the availability and value of surviving dental structure, the existence of a ferrule, the duration of the post cementation, and the ultimate coronal restoration. The notion of "extension for prevention" simplifies treatment operations, however, this also eliminates crucial dentin at the cervical area, leaving natural teeth biomechanically impaired following endodontic therapy.

The concept of minimally invasive endodontics calls for the treatment and prevention of pulpal pathoses and apical periodontitis, while causing the least amount of change to the dental hard tissues. This preserves the strength and function of the endodontically treated tooth with the intent that it will last the patient's lifetime. The structural integrity of teeth treated with endodontics is a critical factor in their long-term survival.

It is apparent that remaining structural integrity of the tooth is a key factor that determines prognosis as it relates to future function of the tooth after restoration. Maintaining strength and stiffness that resists structural deformation becomes the recognised goal of all restorative procedures, especially in endodontics. Appreciation for the biomechanical behaviour of dentin, as the limiting strength factor of any restorative complex, requires the recognition that dentin is weakened unequally by our restorative procedures.

There are, however, currently no developed protocols for minimally invasive endodontics. The aim is to review the current status of non-surgical endodontic procedures highlighting the conservation of tooth structure to enhance longevity after root canal treatment.

More than two decades ago a study was designed to compare the impact of endodontic versus restorative procedures on tooth strength. The stiffness of cusps was assessed when comparing traditional cavity preparations to endodontic access openings on bicuspid teeth. It was found that endodontic access openings by themselves have only a small (5%) impact on tooth stiffness as opposed to any restorative preparation that removes the tooth's marginal ridges (for example, a MOD preparation) reducing cuspal stiffness by 63%. The study identified approximately a 20% loss of tooth strength with each prepared surface. These findings highlight that marginal ridges are a key factor in retaining tooth strength. Another fundamental understanding of dentin behaviour within remaining structure comes with the abandonment of the widely held clinical perception that endodontically treated teeth are more brittle and hence more vulnerable to fracture. An early investigation that demonstrated moisture loss of 9% after root treatment in dog's teeth gave credence to this hypothesis. While animal models have some translation to humans, there is currently an abundance of studies in human teeth showing that the dentin properties of endodontically treated teeth do not differ in any meaningful way from vital dentin. Conversely, the predominant reason that endodontically treated teeth are more prone to fracture relates more than any other attribute to the structural loss of those root treated teeth requiring restoration. Collectively, these studies show minimal dehydration effects from pulpal removal and demonstrate biomechanical behaviours in strength and toughness testing that are similar to vital dentin.

Unfortunately, structural loss alone cannot answer every clinical question that relates to dentin failure. The relevance of fatigue as a main mechanism for tooth fracture and the resistance of dental tissues to both the initiation and propaga-

tion of cracks is an important research area. Recently, investigations have focused on the impact of chemical factors such as irrigants and medicaments on dentin; the effects of bacteria on the matrix of dentin; structural loss; the effect of post and core restorations and the results of age changes in dentin. Of note, there is a reduction of up to 50% in the tensile strength and fatigue strength of coronal dentin in seniors (over 55 years) when compared to that of young adults. Similarly, the resistance to propagation of fatigue cracks in dentin decreases with increasing patient age and the incremental rate of crack extension is up to 100 times greater in seniors.

Biomechanical Behaviour of Dentin

A vital cellular component, the dentine houses the cellular processes of the pulp-dwelling cells known as odontoblasts. Biomechanics is the branch of engineering mechanics that deals with the study of biological structures and their functions in terms of mechanical principles.

Natural collagen provides strength, whereas the inorganic component of dentin can withstand the hardness and high compressive properties of dentin because of its water-based nature. Tensile stress in compression is greater than tensile stress in tension. The small pulpal environment and fluid in dentinal tubules all work together to prevent cracks in the dentin from occurring. Endodontic therapy may cause a decrease in dentin water content, which might lead to dentin tissue contraction and the formation of cracks and fractures that could lead to tooth breaking. With this objective in mind, pericervical dentin preservation has been advocated for in endodontics using the MIE method maintaining dentin, which acts as a stress-transmitting conduit, may increase the strength of the tooth. Removal of dental hard tissues such as the oblique ridges, peri-cervical dentin, and the thinning of marginal surfaces for clinical convenience may increase the risk of tooth breakage, they developed this procedure.

Teeth that physically fail through a vertical or unrestorable root fracture do not have to undergo endodontic treatment to experience this outcome. It has been demonstrated in the dental literature that all teeth, especially molars, can fracture without any endodontic treatment, and while some state this is not a common finding there are others who declare that the incidence is under-reported. However, when fracture occurs, it will inevitably have a devastating effect on both the periodontal attachment and the bone adjacent to the fracture. Once a fracture begins in the root and continues it is characterised by involvement of the root canal in the fracture progression; bacterial contamination of the failed section; food-debris, cements, necrotic tissue and bacteria; as well as inflammation associated with a reactive periodontium. Studies involving Chinese populations have reported that fractures may occur within teeth with vital pulps in individuals with excessive or repetitive oral chewing habits. This is in agreement with the author who also suggested heavy masticatory forces as a cause for root fracture. In addition, root fractures seem to be more prevalent in seniors and male populations; pre-existing attrition is often a component of the condition.

To be continued.....

(It's a review of literature and not an original article)